

MATERIAL PRESERVATION VS MATERIAL CONSERVATION: ANALYSIS AND CONSERVATION OF ARCHEOLOGICAL MATERIAL OF THE SITE SC-NAUF-01, SANTA CATARINA, BRAZIL

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Marco Polo describes a bridge, stone by stone. – What is the Stone which maintain the bridge? Kublai Kan asks.

– The bridge is not maintained by this or that stone – Marco answers -, but by the arc line that they made. Kublai remains silent, thinking. After he adds:

– Why do you talk about stones to me? The only one that is important it is the arch.

Polo answers:

– Without stones there is no arch”

The invisible cities, Italo Calvino.

Abstract: *This work presents, in a brief form, the criteria used to analyse and conserve the archaeological material exhumed from the site SC-Naufragados¹-01. This site is located in Baía Sul² in Florianópolis, Santa Catarina, Brazil, and it has been studied since 2010. From there it was withdrawn some archaeological material and their analysis had as aim identify the integrity degree of the pieces to, after, developing a suitable action plan to the conservation of the archaeological material. Some points lead this process: the conservation of archaeological material and its disclosure to the community and the development and adaptation of conservative technics and the analysis of the pieces in a historical perspective, where was highlighted, from a structured context, the reading of the artefacts, in this work understood as a representation of a historical period which involves the meeting between different cultures.*

Keywords: *Underwater Archaeology, Submerged Cultural Heritage, Conservation and Preservation*

Resumo: *Este artigo apresenta, de forma breve, os critérios adotados para a análise e conservação do material arqueológico exumado do sítio SC-Naufragados-01. Localizado na Baía Sul de Florianópolis, Santa Catarina, Brasil, que se encontra em estudo desde 2010. Nele registraram-se alguns materiais arqueológicos cuja análise permitiu identificar o grau de integridade das peças, para posteriormente, desenvolver um plano de ação adequado à conservação do material arqueológico. Dos pontos que nortearam este processo pautam-se: a conservação do material arqueológico e a sua extroversão para a comunidade, passando pelo desenvolvimento e adaptação de técnicas de conservação e a análise das peças numa perspectiva histórica, onde se destacou, a partir de um contexto estruturado, a leitura dos artefatos, aqui entendidos como a representação de um período histórico que envolveu o encontro entre culturas distintas.*

Palavras-chave: *Arqueologia Subaquática, Património Cultural Submerso, Conservação e Preservação*

INTRODUCTION

This work presents the methodology of analysis and conservation of stone and metal pieces exhumed from the archaeological site SC-NAUF-01, in southern Florianópolis, in Santa Catarina, Brazil, in 2010.

The main aim of this project presupposed an archaeological investigation based on theoretical parameters of the historic archaeology (Orser, 2000), with post-procedure bias (Hodder, 1994) which orient the hypothesis of the research in a wide area to be prospected and interpreted starting from comparison analyses by sampling (Gould, 2001; Fontenoy, 1998). The area studied presents several underwater and land archaeological sites previously identified (Juliani *et alli*,

¹ T.N.: Location name that means shipwrecked.

² T.N.: It is also a location name. Is located in South Bay.

Figure 1 – Location of the archaeological site where treated materials were exhumed

2008). Some questions orient this research and they are going to be answered as the search progress and, above all, it is imperious know how the site was formed as well as the several evidences which compound it.

The archaeological station context has been evaluated by the group that is investigating the place. Some members of this group subscribe this article and they give relevance to structural and of the artefacts relations that compound the place as well as its preservation. The team appealed to designations purposed by Schiffer (1987) to understand post-depositional processes. This author distinguished them in cultural (Transformations – C) and natural (Transformations – N). Cultural Transformations involve deliberated or accidental human activities; Natural Transformations present natural causes that determine changes in the archaeological register. These distinctions are fundamentals to an adequate perception of human life and the past events, as in surface and posteriorly after submersion. These same procedures have several implications in the affection and preservation of the objects and they must be properly analysed during the intrusive archaeological processes. In this way, it is imperious the monitoring of experts in the conservation area to perform an efficient and safe extraction of the traces.

Starting from these theoretical and methodological presumptions and consciously that the historical objects and subjects emerge from discursive constructions (Rago, 2004), it was developed a small intrusive intervention. Some objects were emerged after these contextual register and the analysis of these conservation state. These objects were made in stone and metal and their preservation was in charge to GRUPEP-UNISUL.³ The

³ T.N.: Archaeological Research group – UNISUL, Universidade do Sul de Santa Catarina.

analysis was properly performed and their preservation processes was initiated in partnership with the Laboratory of Archaeology and Conservation of Underwater Heritage of Instituto Politécnico de Tomar.⁴

Altogether, there are four artefacts in stonework and some ballast stone, and a small fragment in metal.

The methodology used to clean the pieces in stone was based on Almeida (2005), Hamilton (1999) and Monteiro (2010; 2011). The aim of this analysis was identify the integrity degree of the pieces for, posteriorly, develop an adequate action plan to the conservation of the material.

Archaeological and historical data documented until this moment raise the hypotheses that several shipwreck occurred in that region, some of them was widely described in the chronicles of discovering and in another historical publications (Staden, 1974; Idem, 1992; Duran, 2008; Farias *et alii*, 2012). In a detailed documental research about the area where the site SC-NAUF-01 was observed, it has been registered the presence of a shipwreck from 16th Century. It belonged to a navy sailing toward the Strait of Magellan commanded by Diego Flores Valdés and Pedro Sarmiento de Gamboa (Boiteux, 1912 and 1919).

In fact, during the works of investigation, it was possible to produce a planialtimetric survey of the shipwreck. The plotting of traces allowed evaluating the current situation of the archaeological site. Current data were compared with historical data obtained and they point to a probable relation with reported data, what made this local a world important place. After the confirmation, it preservation will become indispensable.

⁴ T.N.: Polytechnic Institute of Tomar.

Frame 1 – Categories of artefacts identified in SC-NAUF-01

Categories of artefacts	Description
Category 1 – metal	Bronze cannon evidenced in the north side of the shipwreck; metal fragments on the ballast.
Category 2 – artefacts in stonework	In the north side was evidenced a joint of four stones. They were three metres far from the cannon and it is possible they could be used as constructive marks and adornment to compose some kind of architectonic work.
Category 3 – Ballast stones	They compound the central part of the shipwreck.
Category 4 – Wood	Wooden plank measuring 100 x 30 centimetres and smaller in 0.50 x 0.10 centimetres.
Category 5 – Pottery	Pottery fragments.

In order to proceed a best identification of the historical and archaeological elements, it was essential develop a systematic excavation with detailed recognizing of the artefacts, as the case of the bronze cannon, whose date of foundry is 1563. Beyond this work, GRUPEP maintains a primary concern with exhaustive bibliographical research in an unceasing finding more documents and data which present reports about navigations and ship that sailed by Ocean Atlantic. These bibliographical research approach navigations toward Brazil Southern and Austral America, passing by Santa Catarina in several historic periods, particularly the documents referents to the shipwrecks in 16th Century, mainly those that occurred during the Iberian Union under government of D. Phillip II, wherewith was related this archaeological site.

BRIEF REPORT OF FIELD RESEARCH – INITIAL INTERPRETATIONS

The material analysed in this article is from archaeological site SC-NAUF-01 localized in Baía Sul Southern, near to Ponta dos Naufragados and Ilha do Papagaio Grande, in geographic coordinates 27°49 S / 048°34 W, in Florianópolis-SC. The research was performed in partnership of Barra Sul, a non-governmental Organization and GRUPEP-Archaeology/UNISUL. The Project was submitted to IPHAN⁵ in 2010 and it previses the prospection of Baía Sul and the excavation of sites that were found within the area of the Project. After this stage, the Project became interdisciplinary and integrated experts from different areas. In 2011 was developed an agreement between UNISUL and Instituto Politécnico de Tomar, which involve the Laboratory of Archaeology and Conservation of Underwater Heritage in the treatment and analysis of recovered material, which resulted in this article.

Also around this time, it was performed the recognizing and inspection of the place with electronic prospections using Full Circle scanning sonar, Side Scan Sonar, echobathymeter and Global Positioning System equipment, metal detector and systematic diving in potential areas for archaeological sites indicated by these devices (Farias *et alli*, 2012).

Archaeological traces of SC-NAUF-01 are dispersed in an area of approximately twenty two metres of width by

thirty metres of length atop of Sandy bottom covered by molluscs and algae. They are two kilometres from the shoreline; in this case, represented by Praia do Sonho;⁶ one quilometre from Ponta dos Naufragados and three hundred metres from Praia do Defunto,⁷ in Ilha de Santa Catarina.⁸ This place is featured by the constant movement of sandbanks because of the ocean currents that crossed the canal (Farias *et alli*, 2012).

Over there was performed the following activities based on the methodologies purposed by Bass (1971); Blot (1998); Green (2004); Renfrew and Bahn (2007); Bowens (2009):

- Delimitation of the site with metal detector;
- Total scanning using direct prospecting technic;
- Definition of a point zero in the more elevated part of the site;
- Implantation of poitas⁹ in order to demarcate the research area;
- Georeferencing of poitas by total GPS station;
- Photo mosaic of site;
- Mapping of ballast and dispersed traces;
- Analysis of preservation state of objects *in-situ*;
- Emersion of objects with potential to identify the shipwreck;
- Conservation of exhumed objects.

Through the prospection, it was possible identify five categories of artefacts presented in Frame 01 in the archaeological site area.

From the observed material, it was removed the four artefacts in stonework, a very rusty object in metal with concretions and some pieces of ballast.

THE CONSERVATION OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL MATERIAL

The preservation of an artefact must be a constant concern for the archaeologist who previses the research

⁶ T.N: Dream beach.

⁷ T.N: Defunct beach.

⁸ T.N: Santa Catarina Island, the Capital of the State.

⁹ T.N.: Kind of weight used in substitution of anchor in small ship.

⁵ T.N: National Institute of Historical and Artistic Patrimony.

Figure 2 – Process of desalination

Figure 3 – a and b – Blazon of Lion and Castile with Portuguese symbol indicating the period of Iberian Union (1580-1640). We can easily observe two lions, one in the inferior right side and another in superior side and two towers on opposite corners of lions. They are crowned at the top. We can observe five Portuguese chines

field performing.¹⁰ Then, we understand that every trace in an archaeological site, when it is removed from this environment, no matter whether is aquatic or in land, it can suffer some kind of deterioration. In the aquatic environment, the degradation parameters of the material are different from the processes in dry environment. The water is a crucial factor, but it can be also a misleading factor. An object that seems stay in good state, in fact, can stay in risk of total collapse. The only thing that maintains the material in its original form is the fact of its pores are filled with water and the loss of this element can lead to the destruction of its internal structure, provoking the deformation and total or partial

disintegration of the object (Monteiro, in press). In this way, it is imperious a pre-evaluation of the materials *in situ* and a storage plan for the materials in medium and long term.

The material from SC-NAUF-01 passed by the follow stages: Storage in containers with water, desalination, and report in appropriate files, analysis and cleaning.

Identification, analysis and conservation of archaeological material

Four stonework was registered and they possibly were used as constructive or adornment elements (Fig. 1, 2 e 3). The general methodology of analysis used followed the precepts of Monteiro (2010, 2011, 2012) and involved, initially, the technical description of the pieces with manual testing of resistance, observation of rocklike mass by naked eye and binocular magnifying glass,

¹⁰ In the sole paragraph of the Article 9 of the Ordinance 07/1988, the State delegates to the researcher total responsibility under the guard of the archaeological patrimony while the Project is in effect, besides, this ordinance provides, in the Article 5, item VII that must be exist a researcher institution responsible by the guard of the collection. In this Project, the responsible institution is the UNISUL through the GRUPEP-Archaeology.

Frame 2 – Description of stonework pieces

Description	Dimension				Material	Production techniques
	Width	Height	Depth	Diam		
Stone with blazon	74.5	93.0	22.0		Granite gneiss stone	Bas-relief sculpture
Triangular stone	74.0	108.0	16.5		Granite gneiss stone	Epigraphy
Sphere 1				24.5	Granite gneiss stone	Sculpture
Sphere 2				25.0	Granite gneiss stone	Sculpture

SC-Naufragados-01 Pedra Triangular

Figure 4 – Stone in triangular shape with bas-relief in Latin where we can read “PHILIPPVS MAXIMVS CATHOLICVS II HISPANIARVM INDIARVM ET REX ANNO 158.2” It is an allusion to King Phillip II

Figure 5 – Example of one of the spheres, possibly to compound an adornments architectonic work.
There is a pyramidal engaging hole that is long-drawn until 1/3 of the piece

identification of concretion types by chemical tests and reporting on appropriate files of analysis involving attributes like: identification, proprieties, register, dimensions, historical and environmental context and conservation state (Frame 2).

After immersed, the material was storage in a polyurethane box, lined with high density EVA¹¹ and covered by a blanket to protect against eventual impacts. According to the analysis performed and the recognizing of pathologies in the material, we can summarize that the state of pieces found is satisfactory taking into account the rock hardness and the long period submersed in salt water. It was detected some chromatic changes, alveolarization, disintegration of cut material produced by concretions, incrustations and abrasion due to the environment changes went to siltation caused by the movement of the tide.

The first process performed was desalination. The pieces passed by a process of changing of total water and constant monitoring of physical chemical parameters. Among them, we highlight the pH (hydrogen potential) which is used to express the intensity of acid or basic conditions in a solution and it is a way to express the concentration of hydrogen ion (Sawyer *et alli*, 1994 *apud* Farias, Correa 2006:11); and the electrical conductivity (CE) represented by the result measure of an electric force given, that is directly proportional to the quantity of

¹¹ T.N.: Vinyl polyacetate.

Figure 6 – The X-Ray allowed identify a fragment of a small iron rod of rectangular hollow section that possibly could be twisted by a rope, visible by traces of empty spaces left on the concretions

salts present in a solution. This process allows monitoring the presence of salts in the object by osmosis process. As the bathing are substituted, the salts are liberated to the solution until maintain in balance, producing variations in the conductivity of aqueous solution. The readings of conductivity, pH and temperature were performed with the devices *HI 98129 – pH/EC/TDS/Temperature with only one tester. Combo pH & EC. Hanna Instruments*, at the same hour of the day.

The cleaning of concretions will be performed after desalination. The aim is remove all substances that causes deterioration process in the pieces or contribute to it happened, like soluble salts, incrustations, vegetation infestation and animal waste; in this way it is possible protect the texture and appearance of the stone. The cleaning will be performed in controlled way, removing only the layers of particles necessities to a good conservation of the stone, avoiding any possible aggression in the piece. The use of chemical products is restricted to the cases with proved necessity in order to avoid any change in the pieces (Almeida 2005:56).

Chemical cleaning will be performed systematically with embedded compresses in hydrochloric acid solution in 10%. The removal of concretions will allow the analysis of details not yet detected.

The metal object was submitted to tests of evaluation of metallic core. The results were negatives indicating total loss of metallic core. Based on this result, it was performed a X-Ray test in order to identify the object involved in the volume of concretions and products of oxidation.

The advanced state of oxidation made impossible the recovering of the object. We made the option for total

removal of the humidity by Muffle in 102°C during 24 hours and posterior storage in a controlled environment.

About ballast stones, they were desalinated and storage in dry place.

FINAL REMARKS

The archaeological process of conservation continues in development. Next stages foresee a deepening in the study of research by intrusive or non-intrusive studies. The problem referred to the identification of the shipwreck needs a best inquest and it only will be possible by the continuing of researches that can identify new traces which corroborate the raised hypothesis of the “La Proveedora”, ship belonged to the navy that followed to the Strait of Magellan and commanded by Diego Flores Valdés and Pedro Sarmiento de Gamboa, during the government of King D. Phillip II.

However, all this process only can be performed with an efficient plan of protection and preservation of the materials that would be recovered. With this aim, GRUPEP/UNISUL has been doing all the efforts to create a Laboratory of Conservation for submerged heritage and with the technical scientific support from Instituto Politécnico de Tomar (Portugal) and its Laboratory of Archaeology and Conservation of Underwater Heritage has been developing the competences to preserve recovered material from this archaeological site.

According to the dynamics and times inherent to the processes of underwater conservation, the objects recovered in 2011 are in treatment yet and we can forecast their exposition to the community in few time.

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